

THEROS

An integrated toolbox for improved verification and prevention of adulterations and non-compliances in organic and geographical indications food supply chain

Grant Agreement Number: 101083579

D6.3: THEROS Communication, Dissemination, stakeholders' engagement and liaison activities (final version)

Document Identification			
Status	Final	Due Date	31 December 2025
Version	1.0	Submission Date	04 February 2026
Related WP	WP6	Document Reference	D6.3
Related Deliverable(s)	D6.1, D6.2, D6.4, D6.5	Dissemination Level	PU
Lead Participant	SEAB	Document Type:	R
Contributors	ICCS, JSI	Lead Author	Eleni Krikigianni (SEAB)
		Reviewers	Marilena Paraskeva (eBOS) Garcia Macarena (KIWA)

This project has received funding under grant agreement No 101083579. It is funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Document Information

Author(s) – in alphabetical order		
First Name	Last Name	Partner
David	Kocman	JSI
Dimitra	Tsiakou	ICCS
Eleni	Krikigianni	SEAB
Irini	Krimpa	ICCS

Document History			
Version	Date	Modified by	Modification reason
0.1	05/11/2025	Eleni Krikigianni	Creation of the ToC
0.2	07/11/2025	Dimitra Tsiakou	Comments and approval of the ToC
0.3	28/11/2025	Eleni Krikigianni	Input in all chapters
0.4	01/02/2026	Eleni Krikigianni	Release of deliverable for peer review & Quality check
0.5	04/02/2026	Marilena Paraskeva, Garcia Macarena, Dimitra Tsiakou, Irini Krimpa	Peer Review & Quality check
0.6	04/02/2026	Sozos Karageorgiou	Quality Assurance check
1.0	04/02/2026	Valantis Tsiakos, Dimitra Tsiakou	Final version to be submitted

Quality Control		
Role	Who (Partner short name)	Approval Date
Deliverable leader	SEAB	04/02/2026
Quality manager	EBOS	04/02/2026
Project Coordinator	ICCS	04/02/2026

Executive Summary

Communication, dissemination, stakeholders' engagement and liaison activities are essential to assure the success of a project as ambitious and visionary as THEROS. Funded under the European Union's Horizon Europe Framework Programme, the aim of THEROS was to implement an integrated toolbox being capable to modernise the process of verifying organic and geographical indications food products. THEROS aimed to prevent adulterations and non-compliances, using various technological innovations and data sources, while demonstrating enhanced security, transparency and interoperability in the quality labelled food supply chain.

This document, titled as D6.3: THEROS Communication, Dissemination, stakeholders' engagement and liaison activities (final version), is considered a dynamic document. It is linked to Task 6.1 "Dissemination & communication" and Task 6.3 "THEROS Ground-Breakers Advisory Board", but also to Task 6.2 "Liaison with EU bodies and other relevant research activities & projects within EU (including projects funded under the HORIZON-CL6-2021-FARM2FORK-01-10, HORIZON-CL6-2022-FARM2FORK-01-11 and HORIZON- CL6-2021-FARM2FORK-01-17 call-topics) and beyond & THEROS knowledge base", within Work Package WP6 "THEROS high impact creation and sustainability".

This document's primary purpose is to provide a thorough summary of the scientific, communication, and dissemination efforts made by THEROS consortium partners during the third year of the project's duration. The main objective of these efforts is to increase awareness and outreach among different target groups about THEROS findings, outputs, and technical work carried out from January to December 2025.

More specifically, the report provides quantitative information on the status of THEROS communication and dissemination channels, tools, and methods, scientific activities conducted, participation in prominent conferences and events, as well as details on clustering and networking activities.

Table of Contents

Executive Summary.....	3
1. Introduction	7
1.1 Purpose of the document.....	7
1.2 Intended readership.....	7
1.3 Document Structure	7
2. THEROS Communication Kit (Channels, Tools & Means)	9
2.1 Online channels.....	9
2.1.1 Project website.....	9
2.1.2 Social Media accounts.....	11
2.2 Dissemination Tools	15
2.3 Communication Means	18
2.3.1 THEROS e-newsletters.....	18
2.3.2 THEROS partners interview series.....	18
2.3.3 THEROS press activities	19
3. THEROS scientific activities	23
3.1 Conducted activities	23
3.2 Upcoming scientific activities	25
4. THEROS participation in Events & Conferences.....	26
4.1 Conference events.....	26
4.2 Workshops, Seminars, Webinars.....	27
4.3 Exhibitions/Booths	28
4.4 Upcoming activities	29
5. THEROS Clustering & Networking activities	30
5.1 THEROS Cluster.....	30
5.2 Cross fertilisation activities	32
5.3 Beyond the Project: Sustainability and Continuity of Cluster Activities.....	33
6. THEROS Ground Breakers Advisory Board	34
7. Evaluation & monitoring of communication /dissemination activities	36
7.1 Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)	36
7.2 Risk management and compliance.....	37
8. Conclusions	40
References.....	41

List of Tables

Table 1 THEROS e-newsletters	18
Table 2 THEROS press activities between M25-M36	19
Table 3 THEROS scientific activities M25-M36.....	23
Table 4 THEROS attended conferences between M25-M36.....	26
Table 5 THEROS attended workshops/webinars/seminars between M25-M36	27
Table 6 THEROS attended exhibition/booths between M25-M36	28
Table 7 THEROS joint activities between M25-M36	32
Table 8 THEROS WP6 risk registry	37

List of Figures

Figure 1 Screenshot of THEROS website-main page	9
Figure 2 THEROS Knowledge Base website section	10
Figure 3 THEROS website analytics	10
Figure 4 THEROS website analytics	11
Figure 5 THEROS Twitter/X account.....	12
Figure 6 THEROS LinkedIn account organic impressions over the last 12 months (January 2025–December 2025)	13
Figure 7 THEROS YouTube Channel analytics.....	14
Figure 8 THEROS YouTube Channel content	14
Figure 9 THEROS Marketplace brochure	15
Figure 10 THEROS roll up banner for THEROS final event.....	16
Figure 11 Post card with THEROS.....	17
Figure 12 THEROS e-newsletter subscription functionality	18
Figure 13 THEROS Campaign videos released (by M36)	19
Figure 14 Overview of projects participating in the EU Cluster for Food Traceability and Trust	30
Figure 15 EU Cluster for Food Traceability and Trust logo.....	31
Figure 16 EU Cluster for Food Traceability and Trust LinkedIn page	31
Figure 17 THEROS KPIs monitoring matrix	36

Abbreviations & Acronyms

Abbreviation / acronym	Description
AB	Advisory Board
CA	Consortium Agreement
DNA	Deoxyribonucleic Acid
DoA	Description of Action
DPP	Digital Product Passport
EC	European Commission
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EU	European Union
D1.1	Deliverable number 1 belonging to WP 1
GA	Grant Agreement
GBAB	Ground Breakers Advisory Board
GI	Geographical Indication
IFOAM	International Federation of Organic Agriculture Movements
JRC	Joint Research Centre
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
Mx	Month x
MS	Microsoft
ORE	Open Research Europe
PMs	Person Months
PO	Project Officer
PU	Public
RnD	Research and Development
SMEs	Small and medium-sized enterprises
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
WP	Work Package

1. Introduction

The current deliverable, *D6.3: THEROS Communication, Dissemination, stakeholders' engagement and liaison activities (final version)*, constitutes a key reference document for all the communication, dissemination, stakeholders' engagement and liaison activities that have been implemented within WP6 of THEROS project, and it is intended as a living document through the project's lifetime.

This deliverable has been prepared and delivered by SEAB, as lead beneficiary of the Work Package 6 'THEROS high impact creation and sustainability', towards recording the contributions from all THEROS project partners.

1.1 Purpose of the document

This document contains all communication, dissemination, scientific and activities performed, attended, organised, and conducted during the third year of the project's duration, by THEROS consortium partners.

1.2 Intended readership

D6.3: THEROS Communication, Dissemination, stakeholders' engagement and liaison activities (final version) is a public deliverable and constitutes a very useful follow-up, addressed not only to the consortium members, but also to any interested reader {i.e., Public (PU) dissemination level}.

It is primarily written for the European Commission (EC), Project Officer (PO) and the consortium members of the THEROS project as a useful update and assessment to THEROS communication, stakeholders' engagement and liaison activities.

Nevertheless, special effort and focus have been, also, given on making this report a stand-alone comprehensible document for the public.

1.3 Document Structure

Section 1 introduces the purpose of the document, the intended readership and the document structure.

Section 2 provides a status description of the THEROS communication and dissemination channels, tools, and means.

Section 3 presents the scientific activities that have been conducted between M25-M36.

Section 4 summarises THEROS attendance and participation in related events, conferences, seminars, workshops, and exhibitions, between M25- M36.

Section 5 describes the performed clustering and networking activities between M25-M36.

Section 6 highlights the interaction with the THEROS Advisory Board.

Section 7 analyses the status of the evaluation and monitoring processes of the THEROS communication and dissemination activities during the last year of the project duration.

Finally, section 8 summarises the concluding remarks of D6.3: THEROS Communication, Dissemination, stakeholders' engagement and liaison activities (final version).

2. THEROS Communication Kit (Channels, Tools & Means)

Since the start of the project, THEROS has developed and put into practice a variety of communication channels, tools, and approaches to share information, build visibility, and meaningfully engage its intended audiences. These activities have been adapted to reflect the needs and profiles of each target group. The summary below presents the key communication channels, tools, and methods used to disseminate THEROS results, outputs, and progress, along with an update on how they have evolved and been maintained during the project's third year.

2.1 Online channels

THEROS project's online channels include the project's website and the social media accounts.

2.1.1 Project website

The THEROS website formed the core of the project's communication and dissemination efforts, acting as a central reference point for stakeholders and other audiences. It provides reliable, regularly updated information on the project's objectives, focus areas, pilot demonstrations, consortium partners, results, and related resources and initiatives. The website is available at <https://theros-project.eu/>.

Figure 1 Screenshot of THEROS website-main page

Since M28 (April 2025), THEROS website has been updated with an additional page (Figure 2) in the main navigation bar, dedicated to the THEROS Knowledge Base. This page includes the THEROS Toolbox, THEROS Pilot Dossiers, the Network of Networks, Practice Abstracts, CookBooks, and Policy Briefs. A detailed description per section is available in D6.5: THEROS knowledge base (final version).

Figure 2 THEROS Knowledge Base website section

According to the THEROS website analytics presented in Figure 3 and Figure 4, the website recorded a total of 3.4k users¹, over the last 12 months of the project, with 15k page views during the same period. The average session duration² is approximately 1 minute and 26 seconds, and a total of 110,088 events were recorded over the reporting period

Figure 3 THEROS website analytics

¹ According to Google Analytics [1], "Total users" is the total number of people who visited THEROS site in a specified date range

² A session in Google Analytics is a group of interactions recorded when a user visits the website within a given period.

Figure 4 THEROS website analytics

2.1.2 Social Media accounts

Since the project began in M01 (January 2023), THEROS has maintained an active presence on three social media platforms - Twitter/X, LinkedIn, and YouTube—to support the dissemination of results and strengthen audience engagement. SEAB established and has been overseeing these channels, ensuring they are closely connected to the project website content. Their performance is tracked on an ongoing basis using platform analytics (quantitative indicators) alongside qualitative review of audience reactions, comments, and feedback. Partner-led content and activities shared through these channels have also helped broaden THEROS visibility online.

2.1.2.1 Twitter/X account

The THEROS Twitter/X account (@THEROS_project) is used to share timely project news, with frequent posts and images contributed by THEROS partners. It showcases key activities, such as consortium meetings, workshops, and public events, while also amplifying related updates by reposting content from other relevant initiatives and projects. Visibility is further strengthened through partner support, as consortium members connect the channel to their own accounts and supply SEAB with news, materials, and highlights of recent achievements to publish. By M36, the account had reached 112 followers (Figure 5). The profile is available here: https://x.com/THEROS_project,

Figure 5 THEROS Twitter/X account

2.1.2.2 LinkedIn account

The THEROS LinkedIn page (@THEROS_project) was established to publish relevant updates, connect with key professional communities, and share the project's insights, vision, overall concept, and progress. By M36, it had reached 454 followers. As shown by the platform analytics (Figure 6), during the last 12 months (January 2025–December 2025) the page achieved approximately 14,000 organic impressions and 600 reactions. The THEROS LinkedIn page is available at: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/theros-project/?viewAsMember=true>.

Figure 6 THEROS LinkedIn account organic impressions over the last 12 months (January 2025–December 2025)

2.1.2.3 YouTube account

The THEROS project also maintains a dedicated YouTube channel (Figure 8) to support its communication and dissemination activities by sharing videos that present key milestones and achievements. The channel serves as a central space for hosting general project videos, pilot demonstrations, and additional audiovisual content, including relevant videos produced by project partners. The THEROS YouTube channel is available at: <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCdXfA8j2Qi2fg-yMh7hUobg>.

Within THEROS YouTube channel, the visitor can have access to:

- 17 project partners' videos
- 4 project pilot videos
- 1 project official video
- 1 OCS video as part of Interreg VI-A IPA program Hungary-Serbia
- 2 webinar/workshop recordings
- 1 conference video

By M36, the THEROS YouTube channel included 21 uploaded videos. According to page analytics (Figure 7), these videos accumulated a total of 1557 views, with an average viewing time of 3.17 minutes.

Figure 7 THEROS YouTube Channel analytics

Figure 8 THEROS YouTube Channel content

2.2 Dissemination Tools

THEROS dissemination materials, produced in both printed and digital formats, support the project's wider communication strategy, helping to meet its objectives and engage key target groups. All outputs follow the THEROS visual identity and comply with the European Commission's communication guidelines [2]. The dissemination kit includes a project fact sheet, a general overview presentation, a brochure, a poster, a roll-up banner, and the project's official project video. These resources are described in detail in D6.1: THEROS Communication, Dissemination, stakeholders' engagement and liaison activities (initial version) and in D6.2: THEROS Communication, Dissemination, Stakeholders' engagement and liaison activities (intermediate version).

During the third year of the project, the following update was made to the dissemination materials (available in THEROS website, under Material Hub>Dissemination material area):

- A THEROS Marketplace brochure (Figure 9) was produced and distributed during the Czech Republic pilot demo and related workshops.

The brochure is titled 'REGIONÁLNÍ SPECIALITY DIGITÁLNÍ TRŽIŠTĚ' (Regional Specialties Digital Marketplace). It features the THEROS logo and the website 'theros-project.eu'. The text explains that the marketplace connects local producers with end customers, offering a wide range of certified organic and regional products. It lists benefits for both customers and producers. For customers, benefits include direct purchase, transparency, quality assurance, and online convenience. For producers, benefits include easy market access, increased visibility, full control over pricing and inventory, and modern sales tools. A QR code is provided for more information, and the website 'trh.regionalnispéciality.cz' is listed at the bottom.

theros-project.eu
THEROS

REGIONÁLNÍ SPECIALITY
DIGITÁLNÍ TRŽIŠTĚ

Co je Regionální Marketplace?

Online tržiště propojující místní výrobce s koncovými zákazníky. **Na jednom místě najdete širokou nabídku** certifikovaných biopotravin a regionálních produktů přímo od farmářů a malovýrobců.

Pro zákazníky

- Přímý nákup od výrobců – čerstvé a kvalitní potraviny.
- Transparentnost – informace o původu, výrobci a způsobu výroby.
- Jistota kvality – napojení na moderní technologie (sledování dopravy, kontrola podmínek přepravy).
- Pohodlný nákup online

Podpora lokálních producentů – každý nákupem přispíváte k rozvoji regionu.

Pro výrobce a prodejce

- Jednoduchý vstup na trh – možnost nabídnout produkty přímo koncovým zákazníkům.
- Větší viditelnost a propagace – vaše značka a příběh se dostanou k širšímu publiku.
- Plná kontrola nad nabídkou, cenami a skladovými zásobami.
- Méně prostředníků, férovější podmínky.

Moderní nástroje – statistiky prodeje, hodnocení zákazníků, flexibilní nastavení dopravy.

Jak to funguje?

1. Zákazník si vybere produkty a provede objednávku.
2. Výrobce/prodejce připraví a označí zboží.
3. Doručení je zajištěno s ohledem na čerstvost a kvalitu.
4. Zákazník má přehled o původu i cestě produktu

Podporujeme zdravé potraviny, udržitelný rozvoj a místní ekonomiku.

trh.regionalnispéciality.cz

Figure 9 THEROS Marketplace brochure

- A roll-up banner was also designed for the THEROS final event (Figure 10).

Figure 10 THEROS roll up banner for THEROS final event

- A postcard was produced to promote the CORDIS Results Pack “Accelerating agroecology and organic farming for a more sustainable agri-food system,” highlighting how working with nature and ecosystem services can boost farm circularity, diversification, and resilience. It also positioned THEROS among EU-funded initiatives using digital tools, such as improved labelling and traceability, to support the transition to a more sustainable and resilient European agri-food system.

2.3 Communication Means

2.3.1 THEROS e-newsletters

The THEROS website allows visitors to sign up for newsletters (Figure 12), which acts as a key digital channels for sharing project news, results, activities, and events. Each issue is distributed to subscribers by email and is also published online in the website's Material Hub under the Newsletter section.

To further increase visibility, newsletter announcements are promoted through THEROS social media channels, including Twitter/X and LinkedIn. By M36, the mailing list included 210 subscribers. Overall, the newsletters presented the project's latest developments and helped ensure stakeholders and wider audiences were stayed informed about major outputs and achievements.

Figure 12 THEROS e-newsletter subscription functionality

Four e-newsletters were launched during the last year of the project, and they are presented in Table 1 below:

Table 1 THEROS e-newsletters

THEROS e-newsletters
<p style="text-align: center;">THEROS 4th e-newsletter</p> <p style="text-align: center;">https://mailchi.mp/f49bf1872dd8/theros-e-newsletter-forth-issue?e=d8f4867928</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">THEROS 5th e-newsletter</p> <p style="text-align: center;">https://mailchi.mp/d56ab9234012/theros-e-newsletter-forth-issue-12748539?e=d8f4867928</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">THEROS 6th e-newsletter</p> <p style="text-align: center;">https://mailchi.mp/64009e3032cf/theros-e-newsletter-forth-issue-12751010?e=d8f4867928</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">THEROS 7th e-newsletter</p> <p style="text-align: center;">https://mailchi.mp/161788fae725/theros-e-newsletter-seventh-issue?e=d8f4867928</p>

2.3.2 THEROS partners interview series

The THEROS Communication Campaign has been launched under the title “Meet THEROS Team”. By M36, 17 of the 17 planned videos (Figure 13) were published on the THEROS YouTube channel and uploaded to the THEROS website in the Material Hub under the Audiovisual Material section.

Figure 13 THEROS Campaign videos released (by M36)

2.3.3 THEROS press activities

Press releases are an important tool for showcasing partner achievements and communicating the project's progress. Between M25-M36, the THEROS team has issued several press releases, as summarised in Table 2. These materials are published on the THEROS website in the Material Hub under the Media Centre section, supporting broad visibility and efficient dissemination of key project milestones.

Table 2 THEROS press activities between M25-M36

Type of activity	Title of publication	Date	Involved partners	Press Clippings (url)
Press article in 4th issue of ECHO magazine	THEROS	December 2024	WIRELESSINFO, SUMAVA	https://www.tc.cz/files_public/elfinder/1120/Echo_dvojstanky_4_2024.pdf

Press release	Press release on the 3 rd THEROS plenary meeting	December 2024	eBOS	https://ebosrnd.eu/ebos-participated-in-the-consortium-meeting-of-the-theros-project/
Interview to Synergy Days2024	Synergy Days 2024 projects: THEROS	January 2025	All	https://www.synergyportal.eu/latest-news/synergy-days-2024-projects-theros
Boletín do CONSELLO REGULADOR DA DENOMINACIÓN DE ORIXE PROTEXIDA MEXILLÓN DE GALICIA. Número 49. Marzo 2025	O PROXECTO EUROPEO THEROS	March 2025	MEXILLON, NTTDATA	https://mexillondegalicia.org/wp-content/uploads/2025/04/mexillon-49_web-1.pdf
Article in https://www.farodevigo.es/	Mexillón de Galicia insiste en garantir el origen	April 2025	MEXILLON, NTTDATA	https://www.farodevigo.es/arousa/2025/04/13/mexillon-galicia-insiste-garantizar-origen-116328830.html
Boletín do CONSELLO REGULADOR DA DENOMINACIÓN DE ORIXE PROTEXIDA MEXILLÓN DE GALICIA. Número 50. Xuño de 2025.	O PROXECTO EUROPEO THEROS	June 2025	MEXILLON	https://theros-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/03/mexillon-50.pdf
Press release on THEROS as part of Seminar "Smart Countryside in Practice" - Earth Sustainer 2025	THEROS a digitální tržiště Regionální speciality	September 2025	WIRELESSINFO, SUMAVA	https://theros-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/09/press-release.pdf
Boletín do CONSELLO REGULADOR DA DENOMINACIÓN DE ORIXE PROTEXIDA MEXILLÓN DE GALICIA. Número 51. Setembro de 2025	DO MAR Á MESA: COMO THEROS ACHEGA CONFIANZA E TRANSPARENCIA AOS MEXILLÓNS	September 2025	MEXILLON, SEAB	https://theros-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/03/mexillon-51.pdf

Press release	Παρουσίαση των Αποτελεσμάτων & Εργαλείων του Έργου THEROS	October 2025	ICCS	https://i-sense.iccs.gr/el/news/%CF%80%CE%B1%CF%81%CE%BF%CF%85%CF%83%CE%AF%CE%B1%CF%83%CE%B7-%CF%84%CF%89%CE%BD-%CE%B1%CF%80%CE%BF%CF%84%CE%B5%CE%BB%CE%B5%CF%83%CE%BC%CE%AC%CF%84%CF%89%CE%BD-%CE%B5%CF%81%CE%B3%CE%B1%CE%BB%CE%B5/
Press release	Workshop THEROS Digitální tržiště Regionální speciality v praxi	October 2025	WIRELESSINFO, SUMAVA	https://www.wirelessinfo.cz/news/workshop-theros-digitalni-trziste-regionalni-speciality-v-praxi/
CORDIS - EU research results	Accelerating agroecology and organic farming for a more sustainable agri-food system	December 2025	All	https://cordis.europa.eu/article/id/462116-accelerating-agroecology-and-organic-farming-for-a-more-sustainable-agri-food-system
CORDIS - EU research results	Digital tools for verifying trust in organic and GI food labelling	December 2025	All	https://cordis.europa.eu/article/id/462127-digital-tools-for-verifying-trust-in-organic-and-gi-food-labelling
CORDIS - EU research results	Agroecology and organic farming, CORDIS Results Pack on Accelerating the transition to a more sustainable and resilient agri-food system	December 2025	All	https://publications.europa.eu/resource/cellar/9b19a96b-eaac-11f0-8d3c-01aa75ed71a1.0001.01/DOC_1
CORDIS - EU research results	Postcard	December 2025	All	https://publications.europa.eu/resource/cellar/1937771e-d7d0-11f0-8da2-

				01aa75ed71a1.0001.01/DO C 1
Press release	THEROS Inovacije u organskoj proizvodnji	December 2025	Univerexport DOO	https://theros-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2026/01/UNIPRESS_2025.pdf
Press Release	eBOS at the Final Plenary and Event of the THEROS Project	December 2025	eBOS	https://ebosrnd.eu/ebos-at-the-final-plenary-and-event-of-the-theros-project/

3. THEROS scientific activities

3.1 Conducted activities

The THEROS consortium has been actively preparing scientific publications and other technical contributions for peer-reviewed outlets and high-impact journals, with the aim of sharing project progress and research results with the academic community. These outputs are intended to strengthen scientific understanding by disseminating both empirical evidence and conceptual work produced within the project.

All publications follow the European Commission's Open Access requirements and guidance [3], ensuring compliance with the Grant Agreement provisions described in Annex 5, Article 17. Accordingly, THEROS supports both self-archiving ("Green" Open Access) and Open Access publishing ("Gold" Open Access) for publications and related metadata.

Access to publications has been ensured for all interested stakeholders, primarily via THEROS public channels (notably the project website) and, where appropriate, through EU-supported Open Access infrastructures such as OpenAIRE.

Table 3, below, provides a comprehensive overview of the scientific activities completed between M25-M36.

Table 3 THEROS scientific activities M25-M36

Title	Authors	Event /Journal	Publication date/ publisher	DOI/URL	Website announcement
Detection of organic apple juice fraud by HPLC and FTIR spectroscopy	Christina Kamarinou, Olga Papadopoulou, Natasa Kapetanakou, Chrysoula Tassou, Anthoula Argyri	IAFP's European Symposium 2025	May 2025	https://theros-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/03/IAFP-2025-THEROS.pdf https://theros-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/03/BOOK-OF-ABSTRACT-IAFP-Europe- -P1-15 -Detection-of-Organic-Apple-Juice-Fraud-by-HPLC-and-FTIR-Spectroscopy.pdf	https://theros-project.eu/iafpeuropean-symposium-2025-06-08-05-2025/
Real-time detection of turmeric adulteration with metanil yellow using a miniaturized NIR sensor	Dimitra Xenitopoulou, Nikolaos L. Tsakiridis, Achilleas Panagiotis Zalidis, George C. Zalidis	Future Foods Journal	December 2025	https://theros-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/09/1-s2.0-S2666833525001571-main.pdf	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fufo.2025.100695

and AI techniques					
Uncovering Organic Apple Juice Fraud: Analytical Insights from HPLC and FTIR Spectroscopy	Christina Kamarinou, Ismini Patsopoulou, Olga Papadopoulou, Natasa Kapetanakou, Chrysoula Tassou, Anthoula Argyri	13th ICPMF international conference	September 2025	https://theros-project.eu/13th-icpmf-international-conference_01-03-09-2025/	https://theros-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/10/ICPMF-2025-POSTER-THEROS.pdf & https://theros-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/10/ICPMF-2025-ABSTRACT-THEROS.pdf
User-centred pilot testing of tools for organic and geographical indication of food products	Maria Alejandra Rubio & David Kocman	8th International IMEKOFOODS conference	22-24.09.2025	https://theros-project.eu/8th-international-imekofoods-conference-in-ljubljana-slovenia-22-24-09-2025/	https://theros-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/09/Shorter-THEROS-Poster-1.pdf
Galician mussel species identification via HRM analysis and ML for automated DNA Classification	Lefkothea Karapetsi (INAB-CERTH), Marios Kyriacou (eBOS), Kyriaki Psara (eBOS), Marilena Paraskeva(eBOS), Macarena Garcia Silva (KIWA), Joaquin Garrido (MEXILLON) & Panagiotis Madesis (INAB-CERTH)	8th International IMEKOFOODS conference	22-24.09.2025	https://theros-project.eu/8th-international-imekofoods-conference-in-ljubljana-slovenia-22-24-09-2025/	https://theros-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/10/Poster-for-IMEKOFOODS-conf_CERTH-1_eBOS_Final.pdf
Real-time detection of turmeric adulteration with metanil yellow using a miniaturized NIR sensor and AI techniques	Dimitra Xenitopoulou, Nikolaos L. Tsakiridis, Achilleas Panagiotis Zalidis, George C. Zalidis	Food Analytics Conference 2025	12.11.2025	https://theros-project.eu/food-analytics-conference-2025_12-11-2025/	https://theros-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/11/FOOD_AN1.pdf
Low-Cost Portable NIR and AI Approaches for Detecting	Achilleas Panagiotis Zalidis, Dimitra Xenitopoulou,	39th EFFoST International Conference 2025	17-19.11.2025	https://theros-project.eu/39th-effost-international-conference-2025_17-19-11-2025/	https://theros-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/11/39th-EFFoST-

Wheat Flour Adulteration with Talcum Powder	Konstantinos Karyotis, George C. Zalidis				Conference-2025-Poster.pdf
---	--	--	--	--	--

3.2 Upcoming scientific activities

Concerning the scientific activities beyond the official duration of THEROS project, the team has prepared and submitted one journal article, as of below:

- Journal: Food Control
- Title: Enablers and challenges to digital verification adoption in Organic and Geographical Indication Food Supply Chains: Lessons from pilot demonstrations
- Corresponding Author: David Kocman
- Co-Authors: Maria Alejandra Rubio, MSc; Dimitra Tsiakou; Jelena Nedeljkovic; Lefkothea Karapetsi, MSc; Svetlana Vitomirovic; Aglaia Liopa-Tsakalidi; Nikoleta Serakioti; Marilena Paraskeva; Kyriaki Psara; Lucyna Lekawska-Andrinopoulou; Joaquin Garrido; Macarena Garcia; Petr Horak; Michal Kepka; Eleni Krikigianni; Valantis Tsiakos; Angelos Amditis; Nejc Vesel
- Manuscript Number: FOODCONT-D-26-00470

4. THEROS participation in Events & Conferences

THEROS participated in a wide range of events and conferences to present project developments, communicate key results, and strengthen collaboration with stakeholders from academia, industry, and research organisations. These forums offer important opportunities for networking, knowledge sharing, and promoting THEROS innovations. The sections below summarise the project's engagement in these activities.

4.1 Conference events

The following Table 4 summarises THEROS attendance in related conferences during the last year of the project duration.

Table 4 THEROS attended conferences between M25-M36

Date	Event	Location	Title of presentation	Involved partners	Description (if available)/url
27-30.01.2025	Prague Week with GeoAI	Prague, Czech Republic	Digital Strategy for Strengthening the Local Food Market, Tourism, and Rural Promotion (Data4Food2030 & THEROS)	WIRELESSINFO	https://theros-project.eu/prague-week-with-geoai-27-30-01-2025/
01-03.09.2025	13th ICPMF international conference	Athens, Greece	"Uncovering Organic Apple Juice Fraud: Analytical Insights from HPLC"	ELGO	https://theros-project.eu/13th-icpmf-international-conference-01-03-09-2025/
22-24.09.2025	8th International IMEKOFOODS conference	Ljubljana, Slovenia	User-centred pilot testing of tools for organic and geographical indication of food products	JSI	https://theros-project.eu/8th-international-imekofoods-conference-in-ljubljana-slovenia-22-24-09-2025/
22-24.09.2025	8th International IMEKOFOODS conference	Ljubljana, Slovenia	Galician mussel species identification via HRM analysis and ML for automated DNA Classification	INAB, EBOS, KIWA, MEXILLON	https://theros-project.eu/8th-international-imekofoods-conference-in-ljubljana-slovenia-22-24-09-2025/
26-27.09.2025	5th International "Organic Fest"	Srpska, Serbia	Panel discussion towards delivering a brief update on THEROS project progress and discussed the pilot	OCS	https://theros-project.eu/5th-organic-fest-26-27-09-2025/

			testing activities in Serbia		
15.10.2025	21st International Festival of Organic Products Biofest	Subotica, Serbia	Presentation & press conference	OCS	https://theros-project.eu/21st-international-festival-of-organic-products-biofest-15-10-2025/
12.11.2025	Food Analytics Conference 2025	Copenhagen	Poster presentation on "Real-time detection of turmeric adulteration with metanil yellow using a miniaturized NIR sensor and AI techniques"	AUTH	https://theros-project.eu/food-analytics-conference-2025-12-11-2025/
17-19.11.2025	39th EFFoST International Conference 2025	Porto, Portugal	Poster presentation on "Low-Cost Portable NIR and AI Approaches for Detecting Wheat Flour Adulteration with Talcum Powder"	AUTH	https://theros-project.eu/5th-organic-fest-26-27-09-2025/

4.2 Workshops, Seminars, Webinars

The following Table 5 summarises THEROS attendance in related workshops/webinars/ seminars during the last year of the project duration.

Table 5 THEROS attended workshops/webinars/seminars between M25-M36

Date	Event	Participation (P) Organisation (O)	Workshop Theme	Involved partners	Website announcement
21.01.2025	Workshop "From Farm to Tourist: Connecting Farming with Gastronomy and Tourism"	(P)	Workshop "From Farm to Tourist: Connecting Farming with Gastronomy and Tourism"	WIRELESSINFO & SUMAVA	https://theros-project.eu/workshop-from-farm-to-tourist-connecting-farming-with-gastronomy-and-tourism-21-01-2025/
21.02.2025	Cluster webinar: Traceability and verification in food supply	(O) & (P)	Traceability and verification in food supply	ICCS/SEAB	https://theros-project.eu/cluster-webinar-traceability-verification-in-

	chains: The technological perspective		chains: The technological perspective		food-supply-chains-the-technological-perspective/
17-18.06.2025	THEROS project	(P)	"DG AGRI Workshop of EU-funded R&I projects relevant		
04.09.2025	EFF-CoP: European Food Fraud Community of Practice Virtual Workshop on Food Fraud Synergies	(P)	for organic farming"	ICCS	https://theros-project.eu/workshop-of-eu-funded-ri-projects-relevant-for-organic-farming-17-18-06-2025/
21.08.2025	Seminar "Smart Countryside in Practice" – Earth Sustainer 2025	(O)	Workshop on Food Fraud Synergies	ICCS/SEAB	https://theros-project.eu/eff-cop-european-food-fraud-community-of-practice-virtual-workshop-on-food-fraud-synergies/
16.10.2025	THEROS CZ Pilot Workshop in Klatovy Validated Digital Marketplace and Traceability Tools in Practice	(O)	Seminar "Smart Countryside in Practice" – Earth Sustainer 2025	WIRELESS INFO & SUMAVA	https://theros-project.eu/seminar-smart-countryside-in-practice-earth-sustainer-2025-21-08-2025/

4.3 Exhibitions/Booths

The following Table 6 summarises THEROS attendance in related exhibitions/ booths during the last year of the project duration.

Table 6 THEROS attended exhibition/booths between M25-M36

Date	Event	Exhibition (E)/ Booth (B)	Description	Involved partners	Description (if available)/url
30-02.02.2025	ZOOTECHNIA	Booth	THEROS dissemination material was showcased in BIOHELLAS booth	BIOHELLAS	https://theros-project.eu/zootechnia-30-01-02-2025/
06-09.03.2025	AGROTHESSALY expo	Booth	THEROS dissemination material was showcased in BIOHELLAS booth	BIOHELLAS	https://theros-project.eu/agrothessaly-expo-06-09-03-2025/

4.4 Upcoming activities

THEROS recognizes the importance for the beyond the project related activities, which are focused on advancing its research and dissemination efforts.

Towards this direction, THEROS participation has been already confirmed in the following event:

- Market Advisory Council WG2 meeting, on 5 February 2026 (Presentation of THEROS as part of the EU Cluster for Food Traceability and Trust).

5. THEROS Clustering & Networking activities

THEROS placed strong emphasis on building strategic, mutually beneficial partnerships with sister and related projects, networks, organisations, and initiatives. To support this effort, Task 6.2 was dedicated to coordinating collaboration and liaison activities, working in close synergy with Task 6.1, which provided ongoing support through the project's communication and dissemination actions.

5.1 THEROS Cluster

In February 2024, THEROS embarked on a transformative journey to revolutionize the European Union's food supply chains through innovation, sustainability, and consumer trust. Our initiative began with three flagship projects, THEROS, ALLIANCE, and WATSON, each designed to tackle critical challenges in food safety, traceability, and combating fraud.

As the initiative gained momentum, the cluster, named as "EU Cluster for Food Traceability and Trust", expanded to include ten additional cutting-edge projects, FishEUtrust, SEA2SEE, CUES, TEALHELIX, TITAN, FOODGUARD, ROSETTA, INFOODMATION, DRG4FOOD & EFF-CoP. Together, this collaborative ecosystem of projects leveraged advanced technology, multidisciplinary expertise, and policy-driven strategies to ensure the EU's food supply chains are not only secure but also resilient, transparent, and sustainable.

Figure 14 Overview of projects participating in the EU Cluster for Food Traceability and Trust

The cluster also established a distinct visual identity (Figure 15) by developing its own logo and further expanded its outreach through a dedicated LinkedIn page, available at: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/eu-cluster-for-food-traceability-and-trust/about/?viewAsMember=true> (Figure 16). In the next section, the list with the cross-fertilisation activities between the projects is provided.

Figure 15 EU Cluster for Food Traceability and Trust logo

Figure 16 EU Cluster for Food Traceability and Trust LinkedIn page

5.2 Cross fertilisation activities

THEROS has actively participated in several mutually beneficial liaison activities throughout the last year of the project. These efforts have fostered collaboration and knowledge exchange with various stakeholders and related projects. The following Table 7 provides a summary of THEROS's joint activities during this period.

Table 7 THEROS joint activities between M25-M36

Date	Type of activity	Event	Partners Involved	Related project	Website Announcement
16.12.2024	Telco	4th meeting with Cluster	ICCS, SEAB, JSI	THEROS project along with ALLIANCE, WATSON, FISHEUTRUST, SEA2SEE, CUES, TEALHELIX	
21.02.2025	Webinar	Cluster webinar: Traceability and verification in food supply chains: The technological perspective	ICCS/SEAB	ALLIANCE, WATSON, FishEUtrust, SEA2SEE, CUES, TITAN & TEALHELIX	https://theros-project.eu/cluster-webinar-traceability-verification-in-food-supply-chains-the-technological-perspective/
11.03.2025	Telco	5th meeting with Cluster	ICCS, SEAB, JSI	THEROS project along with ALLIANCE, WATSON, FISHEUTRUST, SEA2SEE, CUES, TEALHELIX, FOODGUARD	https://theros-project.eu/catch-up-meeting-with-our-cluster-11-03-2025/
04.09.2025	Online workshop	EFF-CoP: European Food Fraud Community of Practice Virtual Workshop on Food Fraud Synergies	ICCS, SEAB	THEROS project along with ALLIANCE, WATSON, TITAN, sensAfood IG19145	https://theros-project.eu/eff-cop-european-food-fraud-community-of-practice-virtual-workshop-on-food-fraud-synergies/

21.08.2025	Seminar/ workshop	Seminar “Smart Countryside in Practice” – Earth Sustainer 2025	WIRELESSINFO, SUMAVA	Data4Food2030, PoliRuralPlus, AGRITECH, THEROS	https://theros-project.eu/seminar-smart-countryside-in-practice-earth-sustainer-2025-21-08-2025/
22-24.09.2025	Workshop	8th International IMEKOFODS conference	SEAB, JSI, INAB	EU Cluster for Food traceability & Trust	https://theros-project.eu/seminar-smart-countryside-in-practice-earth-sustainer-2025-21-08-2025/

5.3 Beyond the Project: Sustainability and Continuity of Cluster Activities

Following the official closure of the THEROS project on 31/12/2025, the EFF-COP project agreed to take over the role of Cluster Coordinator from January 2026, ensuring continuity in coordination and joint planning; this transition will be supported by Prof. Saskia van Ruth (EFF-COP Coordinator), and further information on upcoming activities will be shared in due course through the Cluster’s LinkedIn page.

To sustain the EU Cluster for Food Traceability and Trust beyond EU funding and maximise long-term impact, the cluster will keep a visible and active public presence through its dedicated LinkedIn page (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/eu-cluster-for-food-traceability-and-trust/about/?viewAsMember=true>). It will keep organising mutually beneficial cross-fertilised activities like joint webinars, workshops, and participation in events, with support from new members, to strengthen stakeholder engagement. The cluster will also pursue follow-up funding opportunities (e.g., Horizon Europe, LIFE, Digital Europe, and relevant national programmes).

The EU Cluster for Food Traceability and Trust is considered as a community of practice that enables continued knowledge exchange and impact monitoring. Through its continuation it will deepen ties with end-users, producers, regulators, and consumers, to support the practical uptake of all projects’ results.

6. THEROS Ground Breakers Advisory Board

The THEROS Ground Breakers Advisory Board (GBAB) was established as a strategic advisory mechanism to help keep the project closely aligned with real market needs and practical implementation constraints, while also strengthening outreach to external stakeholders and supporting the dissemination of results. Throughout the project, the GBAB was intended to provide expert input on progress and direction, highlight emerging challenges and opportunities in the verification of organic and geographical indication (GI) food products, and offer feedback on the usability and relevance of the THEROS integrated toolbox and related innovations.

In addition, the GBAB was designed to act as a bridge to the broader ecosystem by fostering synergies with sister initiatives and by amplifying key project messages across domains such as organic certification, food integrity, anti-fraud approaches, and blockchain-enabled traceability.

During the first phases of implementation, engagement was pursued through a combination of milestone meetings, targeted requests for comments on selected deliverables, involvement in communication actions (e.g., interviews, webinars, newsletter inputs, and social media amplification), and invitations to provide applied feedback during demonstration and pilot-related activities.

As part of the initial GBAB setup, participation was confirmed from IFOAM - Organics International, UCD School of Biosystems and Food Engineering, and the Joint Research Centre Directorate F Unit F.4 Food Integrity, with additional outreach undertaken to broaden representation among regulators, academia, and industry stakeholders active in traceability and anti-fraud technologies.

However, as the project progressed, the composition and responsiveness of the advisory board evolved. Despite repeated efforts to re-engage some of the initially referenced organisations and individuals through the planned interaction channels, responses were not received in a timely manner, which limited the feasibility of maintaining the original advisory format at the level anticipated.

To ensure that external consultation and validation continued in a meaningful way, the consortium adapted its approach by leveraging liaison and clustering activities, particularly through the EU Cluster for Food Traceability and Trust, to collect structured feedback, test key messages, and discuss relevance, uptake conditions, and stakeholder expectations. This shift effectively broadened the consultation base beyond a fixed advisory board composition, enabling engagement with a wider set of practitioners and project peers, while preserving the core GBAB objective of ensuring stakeholder alignment and practical relevance.

Feedback obtained through these cluster-based interactions informed both technical communication (e.g., how tools and outcomes were presented to end-users) and

dissemination planning (e.g., which results were prioritised for different audiences, and which channels were most effective). In this way, although the advisory structure changed over time, the project maintained continuous external input through an adaptive engagement model, ensuring that THEROS results remained connected to stakeholder needs and that dissemination continued to be supported by credible, sector-relevant perspectives.

In the list below cluster-based interactions, throughout the project duration, are summarised:

- 16–17.05.2024 (Cluster meeting): ESA ESRIN Agriculture Science Cluster Meeting (Partners: ICCS). Website: <https://theros-project.eu/esa-esrin-agriculture-science-cluster-meeting-16-17-05-2024/>
- 11.09.2024 (Webinar): “Securing Our Food Supply Chains: EU’s Innovative Initiatives...” (Partners: ICCS, SEAB; Related: THEROS with ALLIANCE, WATSON, FishEUTrust, SEA2SEE, CUES, TEALHELIX, TITAN). Website: <https://theros-project.eu/securing-our-food-supply-chains-webinar-series-11-13-09-2024/>
- 14–15.10.2024 (Workshop): Synergy Days 2024 (Partners: ICCS; Related: WATSON, FishEUTrust, TITAN). Website: <https://theros-project.eu/synergy-days-2024-14-15-10-2024/>
- 14–16.10.2024 (Conference): FOODTECH Congress (Partners: OCS, SEAB, ICCS; Related: ALLIANCE). Website: <https://theros-project.eu/foodtech-congress-14-16-10-2024/>
- 21.02.2025 (Webinar): Cluster webinar “Traceability and verification in food supply chains: The technological perspective” (Partners: ICCS, SEAB; Related: ALLIANCE, WATSON, FishEUTrust, SEA2SEE, CUES, TITAN, TEALHELIX). Website: <https://theros-project.eu/cluster-webinar-traceability-verification-in-food-supply-chains-the-technological-perspective/>
- 22–24.09.2025 (Workshop): 8th International IMEKOFOODS conference (Partners: SEAB, JSI, INAB; Related: EU Cluster for Food Traceability and Trust). Website: <https://theros-project.eu/seminar-smart-countryside-in-practice-earth-sustainer-2025-21-08-2025/>

7. Evaluation & monitoring of communication /dissemination activities

7.1 Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

Measurable communication and dissemination targets were set from the proposal stage to support the delivery of the project's intended impact. To monitor progress effectively, a Key Performance Indicator (KPI) matrix was created in an Excel spreadsheet and was reviewed and updated each month by the WP6 leader, SEAB. The matrix was stored in the project's internal repository and recorded the KPI names, their current values, and the targets to be achieved by the end of the project. Figure 17 presents the KPI matrix for THEROS up to M36 (December 2025).

COMMUNICATION & DISSEMINATION KPIs MATRIX			
KPIs Names	Current values (M36)	Threshold for the 3 rd year (M36)	Result (3 rd year)
Communication KPIs			
Website online: Unique visitors	5237	1500	☑
Followers on Twitter & LinkedIn	566	500	☑
Views on YouTube	1557	200	☑
e-Newsletters contributed/released	7	7	☑
Total Mailing List Contact Points	210	200	☑
Press activities	24	15	☑
Factsheet	1	1	☑
Standard presentation	1	1	☑
Brochure	2	2	☑
Poster	7	2	☑
Roll up	2	2	☑
Project official video	1	1	☑
Pilot videos	4	4	☑
Partners Interview series	17	17	☑
Dissemination KPIs			
Publishing in Peer-reviewed Journals	2	5	☒
Presenting in Scientific Conferences	43	20	☑
Releasing Technical Publications	10	7	☑
Focus Groups	4	4	☑
Pilot demonstrations evaluation workshops	4	4	☑
Final Event	1	1	☑
Final event participants	120	100	☑
EU events	2	2	☑
Joint/Cluster activities with relevant Initiatives (no of projects)	32	10	☑
Joint/Cluster activities with relevant Initiatives (no of activities)	17	N/A	

Figure 17 THEROS KPIs monitoring matrix

The Communication & Dissemination KPI matrix shows that, by M36, THEROS met or exceeded almost all third-year targets, demonstrating strong outreach and stakeholder engagement. Key communication indicators performed well above

expectations, including website traffic (5,237 unique visitors vs. 1,500 target), social media growth (566 followers vs. 500), and YouTube visibility (1,557 views vs. 200), while planned outputs such as newsletters, press activities, and core dissemination materials were delivered as scheduled. Dissemination performance was also strong, with high participation in scientific conferences (43 vs. 20), increased technical publications (10 vs. 7), successful delivery of focus groups and pilot evaluation workshops (4 each), and a well-attended final event (120 participants vs. 100). The only KPI not achieved was the number of peer-reviewed journal publications (2 vs. 5). Nevertheless, the intended scientific dissemination impact was effectively maintained through alternative, high-value channels: THEROS substantially exceeded the targets for presentations in scientific conferences and technical publications. These outputs ensured that project methods, results, and lessons learned were widely shared with the research community during the project's lifetime, while additional journal manuscripts can continue to progress through the peer-review process after project completion.

7.2 Risk management and compliance

In THEROS, risk management plays a crucial role, especially within WP6. The project's complexity and the interdisciplinary nature of the consortium introduce various risk factors that could impact the successful implementation of the project. Table 8 below provides an updated overview of potential risks associated with THEROS WP6, specifically concerning Communication and Dissemination activities. It outlines the likelihood of each risk, its potential impact, and the mitigation strategies that have been put in place for each identified risk.

Table 8 THEROS WP6 risk registry

Description of risk	Proposed risk-mitigation measures
<p>Low penetration and impact of THEROS brand name to the national and EU and audiences [Likelihood: Low Severity: High]</p>	<p>THEROS team will proceed, at the early stages of the project, with: the development of a precise communication & dissemination strategy [M06], the design of the THEROS brand story [M02] and website [M01] and the creation of dedicated social media accounts [M02]. Statistics on the use of the THEROS webpage and social media accounts will be reviewed periodically to monitor visitors' flow and increase the diffusion in time.</p>
<p>Low engagement of consortium partners in dissemination/communication activities [Likelihood: Low Severity: High]</p>	<p>Close collaboration of WP6 Leader with all consortium partners and continuous triggering of the inactive members through bi-lateral communication and regular WP6 meetings.</p>

<p>Conferences and relevant exhibitions/fairs may be cancelled or postponed [Likelihood: Low Severity: Medium]</p>	<p>Follow closely any relevant opportunities and strive for virtual attendance.</p>
<p>Exploitation, dissemination & comm activities have a lower impact than expected [Likelihood: Low Severity: Medium]</p>	<p>Regular monitoring of the success of dissemination and exploitation, activities, including through given KPIs, adjusting the strategy when necessary. To raise awareness on scope and results, high impact channels and Open Access publications will be used to maximize impact.</p>
<p>Confidential information is disclosed through project's dissemination/communication activities [Likelihood: Low Severity: High]</p>	<p>THEROS has identified and described the required procedures for publishing project's dissemination and communication material since the early stages of the project via its CA. All partners are obliged to follow these guidelines. It has been also established a second level of security (procedures are detailed described in Annex 1), where all information related to communication/dissemination issues must be first approved beforehand by THEROS Project Coordinator, THEROS Technical Manager and the THEROS Communication Manager/WP6 Leader.</p>
<p>Difficulties in AB engagement, because of their internal turnover processes [Likelihood: High Severity: High]</p>	<p>Develop and maintain regular communication with the organizations that advisory board members represent to strengthen relationships and ensure alignment.</p>
<p>WP6 milestones or deliverables are delayed [Likelihood: Medium Severity: Medium]</p>	<p>As part of project management activities, detailed analysis will be done on both global project and lower (WP/Task) project implementation levels. Thus, it will be ensured that cases that could delay any milestones or deliverables are recognised in advance, ensuring timely & effective implementation of necessary corrections in the work plan.</p>
<p>Losing critical staff or partners at crucial point of the project [Likelihood: Low Severity: High]</p>	<p>Given the good reputation of all consortium partners, most of them with proven success records in H2020 Projects, this possibility is considered to be very unlikely. The General Assembly will decide whether the uncovered project activities can be carried out by other partners. If not, then another partner would be recruited.</p>

<p>Overspending by one or more partners [Likelihood: Low Severity: Medium]</p>	<p>This situation will be detected early via management reports under T1.1. If this risk occurs, actions will be considered by the ExB, such as the escalation to the management of the affected partner(s) to mobilise more experienced or better skilled resources, capable of working more efficiently. Ad-hoc recovery plan will be put in place to reach the final targeted budget and requested funding.</p>
<p>Conflict to arise within the consortium [Likelihood: Low Severity: High]</p>	<p>Continuous issue monitoring as well as the importance of ensuring continuous user and stakeholder commitment. Iterative process in the development and demos for issue management, addressing the issues of stakeholder complexity.</p>
<p>Snowball effects in case of delays due to unforeseen factors, e.g., a new pandemic wave [Likelihood: Low Severity: High]</p>	<p>The consortium will employ all means for teleworking and remote collaboration. Therefore, the work in closed workspaces will be reduced to the minimum possible degree. For the cases that face-to-face meetings are unavoidable, the participants will conform with all the necessary healthcare precautions and necessary protocols.</p>

8. Conclusions

This deliverable (D6.3) summarises the communication, dissemination, stakeholder engagement, and liaison activities implemented during the third year of the THEROS project (M25–M36).

Over this period, the consortium maintained a strong and coherent outreach approach across its core channels, website and Knowledge Base, social media (Twitter/X, LinkedIn, YouTube), newsletters, press activities, and audiovisual content, ensuring that project objectives, progress, and outcomes were communicated in a clear and accessible way to diverse target audiences.

In parallel, THEROS strengthened its scientific and technical dissemination through conference participation and publications, while continuing to foster collaboration and cross-fertilisation with relevant EU initiatives through clustering and networking actions, including the establishment and growth of the EU Cluster for Food Traceability and Trust.

Overall performance against the communication and dissemination targets demonstrates strong project visibility and engagement. The KPI monitoring framework, maintained throughout the project, indicates that THEROS met or exceeded almost all targets by M36, reflecting consistent delivery of planned outputs and active engagement with stakeholders through events, newsletters, and online channels.

While the target number of peer-reviewed journal publications was not fully reached within the project timeframe, scientific dissemination was effectively supported through technical publications and extensive conference participation, ensuring timely visibility of results and lessons learned during implementation.

Finally, THEROS put foundations in place to sustain impact beyond the project's end by embedding results in public-facing resources (including THEROS Knowledge Base), maintaining collaboration through the cluster, and enabling continuity of coordination and engagement activities after project closure.

References

- [1] Google Analytics, Dimensions and metrics: [GA4] Understand user metrics available at: <https://support.google.com/analytics/answer/12253918?hl=en> (Last Access 01/02/2026).
- [2] Communicating about your EU-funded project, available at: https://rea.ec.europa.eu/communicating-about-your-eu-funded-project_en (Last Access 01/02/2026).
- [3] EC Research & Innovation Participant Portal Glossary/Reference Terms, available at: <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/support/glossary> (Last Access 01/02/2026).

Disclaimer of Warranties

'This project has used a standard methodology already developed in MOSES project (Grant Agreement number: 861678) and EVENTS project (Grant Agreement number: 101069614), following EU recommendations. Ad hoc modifications were added to comply with the Grant Agreement conditions for THEROS (Grant Agreement number: 101083579).'